
TAXONOMY OF *AGAPANTHIA BOEBERI* (FISCHER VON WALDHEIM, 1806) (COLEOPTERA: CERAMBYCIDAE)

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ABSTRACT: *Agapanthia (Epoptes) boeberi* (Fischer von Waldheim, 1806) is accepted with 6 subspecies: *A. b. boeberi* (Fischer von Waldheim, 1806) - type locality: Russia, "Sarepta" - south suburbs of Volgograd; *A. b. selengensis* Danilevsky, 2021 - type locality: Russia, Transbaikalia, Novoselenginsk environs; *A. b. cynarae* (Germar, 1817) - type locality: Dalmatia and Sicily ("bei Fiume und auf der Insel Arbe entdeckt, ich erhielt sie bei Spalato, Ragusa und Cattaro in Dalmatien"); *A. b. diversicornis* Pic, 1927, nom. rest. - type locality: Albania; *A. b. slamai* Lazarev, ssp. n., type locality: Grece, Peloponnese, Kariopolis, near Gythion; *A. b. michaeli* Sláma, 1986 - type locality: Crete, Voutas.

KEY WORDS: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, taxonomy, distribution, new subspecies, name restored

The first oldest name of the species *Saperda boeberi* Fischer-Waldheim, 1806 was traditionally ignored by all modern authors. They (Küster, 1846; Mulsant, 1862; Gemminger & Harold, 1873; Ganglbauer, 1884; Pic, 1910; Reitter, 1913; Aurivillius, 1923; Breuning, 1961; Plavilstshikov, 1965, 1968; Villiers, 1978; Lobanov et al. 1982; Sláma, 1986; Sama, 2003; Löbl & Smetana, 2010; Danilevsky, 2020) used the next available name *Saperda cynarae* Germar, 1817 in valid form as *Agapanthia cynarae* (Germar, 1817). *Agapanthia boeberi* (Fischer-Waldheim, 1806) was also used from time to time: Winkler, 1929: 1213; Kantardjiewa-Minkova, 1934: 138; Roubal, 1936: 424; Heyrovský, 1937: 90; Csiki, 1940: 268; Depoli, 1940: 319; Villiers, 1959: 10; Mikšić, 1963: 139. So, it cannot be regarded as "nomen oblitum" as the oldest name was used as valid after 1899 (Article 23.9.1.1. - ICZN, 1999). So, the present valid name of the species is *Agapanthia boeberi* (Fischer-Waldheim, 1806) with type locality Sarepta environs (now the suburb of Volgograd) in lower Volga River Valley.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Material was collected manually. Specimens used in morphological studies were killed by ethyl acetate. All photographs were taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1-30.5 mm 1:2.8-4.5 and microscope AmScope SM745NTP. The illustrations were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20.

Acronyms of collections:

MD - collection of M.L. Danilevsky (Moscow)

ML - collection of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow)

OP - collection of O.V. Pak (Donetsk)
SM - collection of S.V. Murzin (Moscow)
VG - collection of V.Yu. Gazanchidis (Moscow)
ZMM - collection of Zoological Museum of Moscow University

RESULTS

List of subspecies of *Agapanthia (Epoptes) boeberi* (Fischer von Waldheim, 1806)

1. *Agapanthia (Epoptes) boeberi boeberi* (Fischer von Waldheim, 1806)
Type locality. Russia, "Sarepta" - south suburbs of Volgograd.
2. *Agapanthia (Epoptes) boeberi selengensis* Danilevsky, 2021
Type locality. Russia, Transbaikalia, Novoselenginsk environs.
3. *Agapanthia (Epoptes) boeberi cynarae* (Germar, 1817)
Type locality. Dalmatia and Sicily ("bei Fiume und auf der Insel Arbe entdeckt, ich erhielt sie bei Spalato, Ragusa und Cattaro in Dalmatien").
4. *Agapanthia (Epoptes) boeberi diversicornis* Pic, 1927, **nom. rest.**
Type locality. Albania.
5. *Agapanthia (Epoptes) boeberi slamai* **ssp. n.**
Type locality. Greece, Peloponnese, Kariopolis, near Gythion.
6. *Agapanthia (Epoptes) boeberi michaeli* Sláma, 1986
Type locality. Crete, Voutas.

Agapanthia boeberi (Fischer-Waldheim, 1806) is extremely variable species. The populations from the type area are rather peculiar and strongly differ from West European populations. Several subspecies must be accepted now.

Agapanthia (Epoptes) boeberi (Fischer von Waldheim, 1806)

(Figs. 1-10)

Saperda boeberi Fischer von Waldheim, 1806: 16 - "Sarepta".

Agapanthia cynarae, Küster, 1846: 67 - "bei Fiume und auf der Insel Arbe entdeckt, ich erhielt sie bei Spalato, Ragusa und Cattaro in Dalmatien"; Gemminger & Harold, 1873: 3176 - "Fiume, Illyria, Russia mer."; Ganglbauer, 1884: 542 (= *decora* Kryn.) - "Süd-Europa, Krim, Kleinasien, Syrien"; Oertzen, 1886: 285 - Attika, Parnasson, Kephalaria, Creat; Reitter, 1898: 134 - "Südeuropa, Krim, Kleinasien, Syrien"; Schaufuß, 1916: 877 - "E. md. Med. R. m."; Plavilstshikov, 1927: 61 - "Transcaucasie, au Caucase et en Crimée"; 1932: 194; Zaitzev, 1954: 19 - Georgia: Borjomi, Tsalka, Tetrtsqaro, Tbilisi, Manglisi, Gagra. Armenia, Azerbaijan, Europe, North Africa; Ogloblin, 1948: 470 - South of the steppe zone east of the Dnieper, Ciscaucasie, Crimea; Breuning, 1961: 186 - "Europe centr. et mer., Caucase, Transcaucasie"; Heyrovský, 1967: 581, 615, part. - "Dalmatien", "Bosnien-Herzegowina", "Montenegro", "Serbien", "Mazedonien", "Griechenland", "Bulgarien", "Albanien": "Iba unterhalb, Krraba, 400 m"; Kryzhanovsky, 1974: 140 - USSR: south of Europe. parts, Caucasus (more often in Transcaucasie); Villiers, 1978: 437 - "Europe centrale et méridionale, jusqu'au Caucase, Asie Mineure"; 2002: 93 - "records from Caucasus, Transcaucasie, Algeria (...), France, Austria and Germany (...) are incorrect"; Lobanov et al., 1982: 269 - North Africa, Mediterranean (Southwestern Europe), Central and Northern Europe, Balkans; Althoff & Danilevsky 1997: 40 - France (without Corsica), Italy (without Sardinia and Sicily), Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia, Macedonia, Greece (without Crete), Crete, Bulgaria, European Turkey, Hungary, ?Avstria, Czechia, Slovakia, ?Germania, Ukraine (without Crimea), Crimea, ?Moldova, South part of European Russia; Kovács et al., 2001: 218 - Hungary: "Somogy county"; Sama, 2003: 93 - "In central Europe

- apparently not recently found, but some old record from Czechia, Slovakia and Hungary could be correct. In southern and south-eastern Europe known from north-eastern and south-eastern Italy, Balkans (from Istria to Peloponnese and European Turkey).”
- Agapanthia boeberi*, Winkler, 1929: 1213 (= *cynarae* Germ.) - Germania occidentalis, Europa meridionalis, Mediterranea; Roubal, 1936: 424 (= *cynarae* Germ.) - “G. oc. E. md. Med. oc. Cri. Ca.”; Villiers, 1959: 10 - Turkey, Amasya. Europe méridionale, Caucase, Asie Mineure.
- Agapanthia* (s. str.) *cynarae*, Pic, 1910: 97 - “Med., Eur. Mle, Russia Mle, Syrie”; Plavilstshikov, 1930: 35, 40 (= *decora* Kryn. = *diversicornis* Pic) - “Mittel und Süd-Europa, Süd-Russland, Krim, Kaukasus, Transkaukasien, Algier”; 1948: 169 - Armenia: Arax valley (Middle and South Europe, Caucasus, North Africa); 1968: 124, 162 (?= *boeberi* Fisch. = *diversicornis* Pic) - In the European part of the USSR, it is found in the extreme south of the steppe zone, including the Crimea, throughout the Caucasus and Transcaucasia. In Western Europe, it is distributed from Hungary and the south of the GDR to the Mediterranean Sea; North Africa; Danilevsky & Miroschnikov, 1985: 386, 391; Mikšić & Korpić, 1985: 101 - “srednja i južna Evropa, Kavkaz, Mala Azija, Sirija.”; Bartenev, 2004: 41 (= *decora* Kry. = *diversicornis* Pic); 2009: 389 41 (= *decora* Kry. = *diversicornis* Pic) - Western Europe, Ukraine (including Crimea), ?Moldova, southern European Russia, Caucasus, Transcaucasia (including Armenia: Araks valley), Turkey, North Africa, Ukraine: south of the steppe zone east of the Dnieper, Crimea.
- Agapanthia cynarae cynarae*, Sláma & Slámová, 1996: 138 - Yug.-Makedonia: “Titov Veles, Gradsko, Josifovo, Valandovo, Stari Dojran, Bogdanci”, Makedonia (east): “Aj. Athanasios, Pendapoli, Granitis”, Makedonia (central): “Lachanas, Kilkis, Dorcas, Litochoro, Aj. Prodomos, Platomos, Leptokaria, Makrokomi”, Makedonia (west): “Agrilio, Anixi”, Thessaly: “Omolio”, Greece: “Amfiklia, Parnassos, Mendenitsa”, Peloponnese: “Kalavrita, Chelmos, Kerpini, Vourvoura, Sparti, Tripoli, Gorani, Arna, Tripi, Artemisia, Messini, Rachae, Karkalu, Vitina, Githio”.
- Agapanthia (Agapanthiella) cynarae*, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004: 127.
- Agapanthia (Epopetes) cynarae cynarae*, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 215 - Azerbaijan, Albania, Armenia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Germany, Greece, Georgia, Hungary, Italy, Macedonia, Slovenia, Romania, Slovakia, Russia: South European Territory, Turkey, Ukraine, Serbia and Montenegro; Shapovalov, 2012: 187; Danilevsky, 2020b: 301 - south of European Russia, Western Siberia, Ukraine, Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Western Europe.
- Agapanthia (Epopetes) cynarae cynarae*, Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 222 - “Europa centro-meridionale orientale. Dall’Italia alla Turchia europea ed alla Russia meridionale”.
- Agapanthia (Epopetes) cynarae*, Shapovalov, 2012: 187 - South of the European part of Russia in the east to the Southern Urals, southern Trans-Urals, Northern Caucasus”, Eastern Siberia (Selenginsk), Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, ?Northwestern Kazakhstan; Kasatkin, 2020: 242, 243.

Type locality. Russia, Sarepta environs (now south suburb of Volgograd).

Big species with peculiar color of 3rd antennal joint – its cuticle about totally black, only narrow basal ring could be reddish and here with white pubescence; basal parts (about basal halves) of 4th-12th joints usually reddish, red or red-brown, sometimes completely black, usually with dense white pubescence; 3rd joint with a row of long dense black erect setae along its whole length, becoming denser distally, sometimes erect setae are spread along 4th joint too; antennae rather long, in males overpassed elytra by 7th (sometimes- 6th) or 8th joints, in females by 9th or 10th joints; elytra can be sharpened apically in certain populations (Kazakhstan) or widely rounded in others (Peloponnese, Bulgaria); elytral pubescence relatively uniform, dense, yellowish, hardly spotted, becoming much denser along curved lateral margin; grey humeral stripe often more or less distinct; erect setae poorly developed and can be clearly seen near elytral bases

only or back to elytral middle; body length in males: 11.8-21.4 mm, body width: 3.0-5.4 mm, body length in females: 13.6-23.2 mm, body width: 3.4-6.3 mm.

Distribution. Southeast Europe: South Italy, Slovenia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia, Macedonia, Montenegro, Albania, Greece, Bulgaria, Hungary, Czechia, Slovakia, Romania, Ukraine. In Russia the species occupies steppe zone eastwards Ukrainian border to the West Siberia; Ciscaucasia (Dagestan, Chechnya, Stavropol and Krasnodar regions); Volgograd Region; south Urals; North-West Kazakhstan; many records for Transcaucasia were published though only one male from Azerbaijan is known to me ("Chatschmas 7.VII.933" - ZMM). The record from "E Tauria" by Krynicki (1834) as *Saperda decora* Krynicki, 1834, and numerous records from Crimea (Ganglbauer, 1884; Reitter, 1898; Plavilstshikov, 1927, 1930; Ogloblin, 1948; Kryzhanovsky, 1974; Bartenev, 1984) need confirmation, as no specimens are represented in Plavilstshikov's collection, neither in any known to me materials. The presence of the species in Iran, Turkey, and generally in Near East is very doubtful (Ganglbauer, 1884: 542, "Süd-Europa, Krim, Kleinasien, Syrien"; Reitter, 1898: 134, "Südeuropa, Krim, Kleinasien, Syrien"; Pic, 1910: 97, "Med., Eur. Mle, Russia Mle, Syrie"; Özdikmen, 2007: 347, 392, Turkey: Bilecik, Içel, Amasya, Edirne, İstanbul, Bursa, Erzurum, Konya, Akşehir, Kocaeli, İzmit; Tekin & Özdikmen, 2015: 128, "Turkey (Bursa): Inegöl"; Varlı & al., 2019: 92, "Western Turkey (Balıkesir)"; Özdikmen & Tezcan, 2020: 470, Turkey: İzmir province, Moeurs; Samin & al., 2020: 2, Iran: Kordestan province, Bijar; Özdikmen & Koçak, 2022: 106, Turkey: Karaman Province). The record of *A. cynarae* for Alger by Lucas (1847) was connected with *A. asphodeli* (Latreille, 1804), according to Villier (1946). According to Sama (2003): "Range. Europe; records from Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Algeria (Plavilstshikov, 1930; Horion, 1974), France, Austria and Germany (Horion, 1974; Villiers, 1978; Bense, 1995; Althoff & Danilevsky, 1997) are incorrect and most likely based on misidentifications with *A. villosoviridescens*. In central Europe apparently not recently found, but some old records from Czechia, Slovakia and Hungary could be correct. In southern and south-eastern Europe known from north-eastern and south-eastern Italy, Balkans (from Istria to Peloponnese and European Turkey). An isolated population in Crete, described as a separate subspecies (*A. cynarae michaeli* Slama, 1986) appears not significantly different from the nominotypical subspecies.". In fact *A. boeberi* was often mixed with *A. asphodeli* (Latreille, 1804).

Biology. According to Bense (1995), larvae are connected with *Carduus*, *Cirsium*, *Onopordon*, but also with *Aconitum* and *Acanthus*; adults are active from April to July, but usually in June.

1. *Agapanthia (Epopetes) boeberi boeberi* (Fischer von Waldheim, 1806)

(Figs. 1-2)

Saperda boeberi Fischer von Waldheim, 1806: 16 - "Sarepta".

Saperda decora Krynicki, 1834: 170 - "E Tauria".

Agapanthia decora, Gemminger & Harold, 1873: 3176 - "Tauria".

Agapanthia cynarae, Jakobson, 1924: 239 (= *boeberi* Fischer von Waldheim, 1806) - "Sarepta"; Bartenev, 1984: 115 - Crimea; Kasatkin & Arzanov, 1997: 67 - North Ossetia; Kalyuzhnaya et al., 2000: 194 - Volgograd region: Kamyshin; Bartenev & Terekhova, 2011: 139 - Kherson Region, Crimea.

Agapanthia (Agapanthiella) cynarae cynarae, Shapovalov et al., 2006: 107 - Orenburg region.

Type locality. Russia, “Sarepta” - south suburbs of Volgograd.

The nominative subspecies is characterized by maximal density of elytral pubescence, and so yellow elytral color; elytra sharpened apically; body length in males: 13.5-21.4 mm, body width: 3.4-5.4 mm, body length in females: 16.1-21.0 mm, body width: 4.2-5.2 mm.

Material. 3 males, 2 females, Chechnya, Starogladkovskaya, Terek River, 22-23.6.1928. Arnoldi - MD; 1 male, Orenburg Region, Sol-Iletsk District, Troitsk environs, 20-30.6.2007, D. Shavkun - MD; 2 males, 1 female, Orenburg Region, Sol-Iletsk District, 8 km SW Troitsk, 21.05.2012, A. Shapovalov - OP; 1 male, 1 female, Orenburg Region, Gay District, Khmelevka, 12.6.2008, A. Shapovalov - ML; 2 males, 1 female, Chelyabinsk Region, S. Troitsk, Zolotaya Sopka, 54°02'46"N, 61°36'34"E, 4-6.6.2013, E.Yu. Zakharova - MD; 1 male, 1 female, Kazakhstan, Uralsk, Rozhkovo, 100 m, 15.6.1999, M. Danilevsky - MD.

Distribution. Russia; the subspecies occupies steppe zone eastwards Ukrainian border to the West Siberia (Samara Region, Volgograd Region, Orenburg Region, Chelyabinsk Region), Ciscaucasia (Dagestan, Chechnya, Stavropol Region, Krasnodar Region); East Ukraine; North-West Kazakhstan (Uralsk environs); many records for Transcaucasia were published though only one male from Azerbaijan is known to me (“Chatschmas 7.VII.933” - ZMM); the records from Crimea (“E Tauria” by Krynicki, 1834) need confirmations.

2. *Agapanthia (Epoptes) boeberi selengensis* Danilevsky, 2021

Agapanthia cynarae cynarae, Danilevsky, 2012b: 113 - “Sibiria or./Selenginsk”, “The erect pubescence of 3rd antennal joint is much longer and denser, than in European specimens, so existence of a new taxon cannot be excluded.”, “east (Transural) part of Orenburg Region”, “Sibiria or. Selenginsk”.

Agapanthia (Epoptes) cynarae, Shapovalov, 2012: 187 - “East Siberia (Selenginsk)”.

Agapanthia (Epoptes) cinarae selengensis Danilevsky, 2021: 501 - “Sibiria or. / Selenginsk” (now Novoselenginsk), misspelling.

Type locality. Russia, Transbaikalia, Novoselenginsk environs.

A single female known; elytral pubescence very dense, similar to the nominative subspecies; pale antennal parts dark-red; erect pubescence of 3rd antennal joint is much longer and denser, than in European specimens, apex of 3rd antennal joint with distinct setae tuft; 4th joint also with numerous dense setae; body length: 18.0 mm, width: 4.0 mm.

Material. Holotype, female with the label: “Sibiria or. / Selenginsk” (now Novoselenginsk) - ZMM.

Distribution. Russia, Transbaikalia, Novoselenginsk env.

3. *Agapanthia (Epoptes) boeberi cynarae* (Germar, 1817)

Saperda cynarae Germar, 1817: 222 - “bei Fiume und auf der Insel Arbe entdeckt, ich erhielt sie bei Spalato, Ragusa und Cattaro in Dalmatien”; Germar, 1825: 9 - “Croatia, Dalmatia”.

Agapanthia cynarae, Gaubil, 1849: 182 - “Dalmatia”; Mulsant, 1862: 353 - “Var”; Csiki, 1905: 63 (= *decora* Kryn., = *verecunda* Chevrl.)- “Budapest”, “Pécs”, “Kassa”, “Plavisevicza, Gerebencz”, “Zágráb, Bukova Kusa”, “Fiume, Buccari, Carlomagno, Zengg”; Müller, 1907: 686 - “Paklenica, Zara, Pridraga, Traù, Spalato, Ragusa, Castelnuovo, Budua, Arbe, Brazza, Lesina”; Cameron M. & Caruana Gatto, 1907: 402 - Malta: “Fort Manoel”, “Corradino”; Reitter, 1913: 66 - “Rheinprovinz, Nassau; sonst in Südeuropa”;

Pic, 1927b: 163, part - "Macédoine: Arapli" [new name Nea Magnisia, 40°41.3'N 22°50.6'E], "Albanie: environ de Koritza"; Picard, 1929: 138, 140 - "Montagnes du midi de la France. Hautes-Alpes; montagnes du Var; Cévennes méridionales; Pyrénées-Orientales; Hautes-Pyrénées"; Portevin, 1934: 174 "Montagnes de la France méridionale, des Hautes-Alpes aux Hautes-Pyrénées"; Demelt & Schurmann, 1964: 39 - "Kanegra, Savudrija, Limski-Kanal"; Heyrovský, 1967: 581, 615, part. - "Dalmatien", "Bosnien-Herzegowina", "Montenegro", "Serbien", "Mazedonien", "Griechenland", "Bulgarien", "Albanien": "Iba unterhalb, Krraba, 400 m"; Villiers, 1978: 431, 437 - "Rare en France, seulement dans les montagnes du midi"; Sturani, 1981 - Italy; Ganev, 1985: 151 - "Kressna-Schlucht", "Borovetz"; 1986: 311 - "Svilengrad"; Sama, 1988: 171 - "Francia meridionale, Cecoslovacchia, Italia meridionale e nordorientale, Balcani, Asia Minore, Caucaso, Siria"; Bense, 1995: 388-389 - south of Western Europe (from France to Greece and Bulgaria) and its center; Comelade, 2000: 49; Hegyessy, 2000: 278 - "Budapest - Solymár"; Vives, 2000: 428 - ?Península Ibérica; Jeniš I. 2001: 260-261; Mifsud, 2002: 167 - "Malta"; Brelih et al. 2006: 9, 313 - Slovenia: "Slovenija: Julijska krajina; Kras"; "Istra: Črni Kal; Gažon; Hrastovlje; Petrinje; Slavnik", "Primorsko-Brestovica pri Povirju; Gabrovica, Komen; Gorica; Lipica; Lokev; Opatje selo; Sežana"; Migliaccio et al., 2007: 39 - "Bulgaria: Common from 0 to 1300 m a.s.l."; Serafim & Chimişliu, 2010: 118, 128 - "Oltenia (South-Western Romania)"; Serafim, 2010: 239, 268 - "Croatia, Krk island", "Clisura Dunării (Danube Clisura) is situated between Nera river in the West, and Gura Văii in the East", "Danube Clisura (Oreva and Slătanic)"; & Perović, 2010: 127 - "Vozilčići, Eastern Istria, Croatia"; Zamoroka & al., 2012: 1167 - Western Podillya, Ukraine: "West Pokuttya", "Medobory"; Pavičević et al., 2015: 84 - "Serbia"; Pesarini C. & Pesarini F., 2016: 67 - Italy: Abruzzo, Calabria; Sláma, 2017: 65 "Graecia, Thes., Omolio"; Kostova, 2019: 81 - "Sredna Gora Mountains (Bulgaria)"; Zamoroka, 2022: 64 - "Ukraine".

Agapanthia boeberi, Kantardjiewa-Minkova, 1934: 138 (= *cynarae* Germ.) - Strandzha Mountain, Kalovo, Chirpan, Dupnitsa, Rila Mountains, Kresna, Ali Botush, Marino pole, Petrich; Depoli, 1940: 319 (= *cynarae* Germ.) - "Lussin: Curilla", "Lussingrande", "Unie".

Agapanthia (s. str.) *cynarae*, Aurivillius, 1923: 460 (= *decora* Kryn. = *verecunda* Chev. = *delagrangei* Pic) - "Rheinprovinz, Nassau, Südeuropa"; Bringmann, 1995: 68, 71 (= *boeberi*) - Bulgarien.

Agapanthia (s. str.) *boeberi*, Mikšić, 1963: 139 - Slovenija: Julijska krajina.

Agapanthia (*Epoptes*) *cynarae*, Sama & Rapuzzi, 2011: 142 - Italy: Basilicata, Calabria, Puglia, Venezia Giulia; Klausnitzer & al., 2016: 556 - Mitteleuropa; Poloni & Morelli, 2021: 40 - "Abruzzo (PE), Popoli, 42.17°N 13.80°E, 350 m".

Agapanthia (*Epoptes*) *cynarae cynarae*, Georgiev et al., 2015: 82 - "Strandzha Mountain (Bulgaria: Fazanovo)"; 2018: 106 Bulgaria: "Strandzha Mt.", "Sinemorets", "Fazanovo", "2.8 km SE of Duni Resort, 42°20.927'N, 27°43.315'E, 2 m a.s.l.", "Rosenets Park, 2 km NW of Atia vill., 42°26.855'N, 27°33.511'E, 5 m a.s.l."; 2019: 18 "Bulgaria: Petrich, Belasitsa Mt.", "North Macedonia: Dojran vill.".

Agapanthia cynarae cynarae, Sláma, 1998: 347, part. - Czechia, Slovakia; Angelini F. 2020: 189 - "Apulia, Basilicata and Calabria (Italy)".

Type locality. Dalmatia and Sicily ("bei Fiume und auf der Insel Arbe entdeckt, ich erhielt sie bei Spalato, Ragusa und Cattaro in Dalmatien") - so, two rather different regions; a designation of the lectotype is desirable.

The subspecies is characterized by less dense elytra pubescence than in the nominative subspecies, so elytra look dark grey and widely rounded apically; body length in males (available specimens): 13.0-18.9 mm, body width: 3.2-5.2 mm, body length in females: 13.6-19.3 mm, body width: 3.6-5.3 mm.

Material. 1 male, Italy, "Abruzzen, Reitter" - ZMM; 1 male, Italy (PZ), Basilicata, Senise, 300 m, 21.6.1983, I. Zappi - MD; 1 male, Croatia, Istria, Rabac, VI.2002, J.

Lorenc - MD; 1 male, Yugoslavia, Lovčen, 4.6.1980, Z. Hauousal - SM; 1 female, Macedonia, Gevgelija, 12.5.1988, I. Toševsky - MD; 1 female, Macedonia, Debar, 5.7.1975, M. Havlas - MD; 2 males, 1 female, Greece, Haslkidiki, Pevkohori, 3-25.5.2016, V. Gazanchidis - MD; 1 male, Greece, Haslkidiki, Kassandra, Polichrono, 9.5.2016, V. Gazanchidis - MD; 1 female, Greece, Halkidiki, Agios Prodromos, 16.6.1988, M. Sláma - MD; 3 males, 1 female, Greece, Halkidiki, Agios Prodromos, 16.6.1988, M. Sláma - ML; 3 males, Greece, Macedonia, Dorcas, 15.6.1988, M. Sláma - MD; 1 male, 1 female, Halkidiki, Kassandra, 10 km da Kapsohora verso Paliouri, 5.5.1983, M. Berra - MD; 2 males, S Bulgaria, Liubimec, 41°50'N, 26°04'E, 84 m, 25.5.2010, W. Grosser - MD; 2 males, Bulgaria, Kozuch, 10.5.1983, J. Ganev - MD; 1 male, Strouma Valley, S Kozhuh hill, 41°27'N, 23°15'E, 90 m, 2.6.2009, T. Ljubomirov - MD; 1 male, Strouma Valley, N Topolnitsa, 41°25'N, 23°19'E, 80 m, 16.6.2009, T. Ljubomirov - MD; 2 females, Bulgaria, Sozopol, 6.7.1981, M. Havlas - MD; 1 female, Strouma Valley, W Kresnessko, 41°47'N, 23°09'E, 290 m, 1.6.2009, T. Ljubomirov - MD; 1 female, SW Bulgaria, Kresna, 20 km N Sandanski, 5.7.2004, W. Grosser - MD; 1 female, Bulgaria, Kresna defile, 17.5.1983, Ganev - MD; 1 female, Bulgaria, Kozuch, 17.5.1983, Ganev - MD; 1 female, SE Bulgaria, Sinemorec, 26.6.2004, W. Grosser - MD; 1 female, Bulgaria, Damjanica, 23.6.1982, S. Kadlec - ML; 1 female, Bulgaria, Arkutino, 25.6.1984, S. Kadlec - ML; 1 male, Bulgaria, Sandanski, VI.1967, B. Lekeš - ML; 3 males, Bulgaria, Sandanski, VI.1967, B. Lekeš - SM.

Distribution. Most part of West Europe: Italy, Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia, Montenegro, Greece (Macedonia and Thrakia), Bulgaria, Hungary, Romania, Czechia, Slovakia. West Ukraine.

4. *Agapanthia (Epoetes) boeberi diversicornis* Pic, 1927, **nom. rest.**

(Figs. 3-4)

Agapanthia cynarae v. *diversicornis* Pic, 1927a: 1 - "Albanie".

Agapanthia cynarae, Pic, 1927b: 163, part - "Macédoine: Arapli" [new name Nea Magnisia, 40°41.3'N 22°50.6'E], "Albanie: environ de Koritza"; Heyrovský, 1934: 135 - Albania: "Skutari, San G. di Medua", "Tepelene", "Ljumi Skumbin", "Devoll-Tal", "Tomor", "Kerpice", "Bushek"; 1967: 581, 615, part. - "Dalmatien", "Bosnien-Herzegowina", "Montenegro", "Serbien", "Mazedonien", "Griechenland", "Bulgarien", "Albanien": "Iba unterhalb, Krraba, 400 m"; Schatzmayr, 1943: 134 - "Lushnja, Skrofotina, Berat, Fushes Dukati e Skendelliut"; Demelt, 1967: 64, part - Greece.

Agapanthia boeberi, Heyrovský, 1937: 90 - Albania: "Lum i Tiranes, Tirane"; Csiki, 1940: 268 (= *cynarae* Germ.) - "Ipek".

Agapanthia cunerea, Muraj, 1960: 141 - "Zall-ardhë", "Qaf-Mollë", "Pasha Liman", "Bizë", misspelling.

Agapanthia cynarae cynarae, Siering & Shumka, 2015: 462 - Shkumbin Tal und weitere Gebiete bei Librazhd (Albanien): "Togëz"; "Zgosht"; "Dorëz"; Siering et al, 2015: 50 - Prespa-Nationalparks in Albanien: "zwischen Goricë e Vogel und Liqenas"; 2016: 47 - Albania: "P. K. Butrinti; Ksamil und Umgebung", "Küste; Orikum; Rruga Sazani", "P. K. Bredhi i Drenoves", "Zentral-Albanien; zwischen Perrenjas und Qukes", "zwischen L. i Shkumbinit und Straße", "S Gjirokaster; Ebene südlich der Stadt", "S Gjirokaster; Bergland; Krongj", "S Gjirokaster; Pass Q. e Muzines; 536 m".

Agapanthia (Epoetes) cynarae, Plewa et al., 2018: 181 - "County Gjirokaster: Lëshicë at Përmet, 450 m a.s.l.", "County Elbasan: Mirakë at Librazhd, 200 m a.s.l.", "County Elbasan: Hotolisht at Librazhd, 290 m a.s.l.", "County Shkodër: Hani i Hotit at Ivanaj".

Type locality. Albania, according to the original description.

The subspecies is characterized by poor elytral pubescence, elytra with distinct bronze luster, moderately rounded apically; narrow basal parts of many antennal joints under fine white pubescence usually rather dark, nearly black; elytral and pronotal puncturation distinctly sparser; body length in males (available specimens): 13.1-17.6 mm, body width: 3.1-4.2 mm, body length in females: 14.7-19.2 mm, body width: 3.7-4.9 mm.

Material. 3 males, 1 female, Albania, Vlorë county, 3.5 km E Vagalat, 39°45'43"N, 20°09'39"E, 80 m, 6.5.2021, O. Pak leg. - ML; 1 male, S Albania, Vlorë County, Delvinë Municipality, 0.7 km NE Lefterhor vill., Kardhiqit Mts., 39°59'6.73"N, 20°5'57.13"E, 696 m, 18.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - ML; 2 males, Greece, Agia Paraskevi, 22.6.1988, M. Sláma - MD; 1 male, 1 female, Greece, Parnassos, 2.6.1981, M. Sláma - MD; 1 female, Greece, Leptokaria, 15.6.1995, V. Grosser - MD; 1 female, Greece, Kalambaka, Meteora, 25.5.1999, W. Grosser - MD; 1 male, 1 female, Greece, Varentada, 20 km J. [S] Arta, 6.6.1999, W. Grosser - MD; 1 male, Greece, Olympus, 6.7.1991 - SM; 2 males, 2 females, Greece, Tembi valley, Gonni, 24.5.2000, I. Rychlik leg. - SM, ML; 1 male, Greece, Olympos Mts., Vrontou, 26.5.2000, S. Kalúz leg. - SM; 3 males, 2 females, NW Greece, Grevena, 30 km SEE Grevena, 10 km NWW Deskati vill., 380 m, 16.5.2010, A. Napolov & I. Roma leg. - OP; 1 female, Greece, Phthiotis, Ypati, 16.5.2017, V.Yu. Gazanchidis - ML; 1 male, Greece, Boeotia, Arachova, 38°29'41.76"N, 22°34'55.06"E, 1517 m, 18.5.2019, V.Yu. Gazanchidis leg. - ML; 1 male, 1 female, Greece, Boeotia, Arachova, 38°29'41.76"N, 22°34'55.06"E, 1517 m, 18.5.2019, V.Yu. Gazanchidis leg. - VG; 3 males, Greece, Larissa, Ossa Mount, 23.5.2017, V.Yu. Gazanchidis leg. - VG; 1 female, Greece, Amfissa, 26.5.2010, M. Sláma leg. - ML.

Distribution. Albania, central part of mainland Greece (Athens env., Mt. Parnassos env., Agia Paraskevi, Arta env., Kalambaka env., Leptokaria env., Grevena env., Ossa Mt., Olympos Mts., Vrontou env., Ypati env., Arachova (38°29'41.76"N, 22°34'55.06"E), Amfissa env.).

5. *Agapanthia (Epoptes) boeberi slamai* Lazarev, ssp. n.

(Figs. 5-6)

Agapanthia cynarae, Demelt, 1967: 64, part – Greece.

Agapanthia cynarae cynarae, Sláma & Slámová, 1996: 138, part – Yug.-Makedonia: "Titov Veles, Gradsko, Josifovo, Valandovo, Stari Dojran, Bogdanci", Makedonia (east): "Aj. Athanasios, Pendapoli, Granitis", Makedonia (central): "Lachanas, Kilkis, Dorcas, Litochoro, Aj. Prodomos, Platomos, Leptokaria, Makrokomi", Makedonia (west): "Agrinio, Anixi", Thessaly: "Omolio", Greece: "Amfiklia, Parnassos, Mendenitsa", Peloponnese: "Kalavrita, Chelmos, Kerpini, Vourvoura, Sparti, Tripoli, Gorani, Arna, Tripi, Artemisia, Messini, Rachae, Karkalu, Vitina, Githio".

Agapanthia (Epoptes) cynarae cynarae, Plewa et al., 2011: 238, part. - "część kontynentalna Grecji", "Peloponez".

Agapanthia (Epoptes) cynarae michaeli, Steiner & Schmid, 2013: 2, part. - "Griechenland".

Type locality. Greece, Peloponnese, Kariopolis, near Gythion.

The subspecies is characterized by minimal elytral pubescence, so elytra look very dark, widely rounded apically; narrow basal parts of antennal joints under fine white pubescence reddish; elytral and pronotal puncturation about as dense as in *A. b. diversicornis* Pic; body length in males (available specimens): 15.3-21.2 mm, body width: 3.4-5.3 mm, body length in females: 17.5-23.2 mm, body width: 4.5-6.3 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The new taxon is close to *A. b. diversicornis* Pic, but bases of antennal joints reddish and elytral pubescence rather sparser; it differs from *A. b. michaeli* Sláma by darker bases of antennal joints and more rounded elytral apices.

Material. Holotype, male, Greece, Peloponnese, Kariopolis, near Gythion, 2.6.1981, M. Sláma - ML; 66 paratypes; 3 males, 4 females, with the same label - ML; 8 males, 6 females, Greece, Peloponnese, Kariopolis, near Gythion, 3.6.1981, M. Sláma - MD; 4 males, 2 females, with the same label - ML; 1 male, 4 female, Greece, Peloponnese, Kalavrita, 5.6.1981, M. Sláma - MD; 15 females, Greece, Peloponnese, Vourvoura, 5.6.1981, M. Sláma - ML; 1 male, 1 female, Greece, Peloponnese, Gythion, 6.6.1981, M. Sláma - ML; 1 female, Greece, Panacheikon, Morea, VI-VII, A. Heyne - MD; 1 male, 1 female, Greece, Peloponnese, Petralona, Minthi Mts., 800 m, 7.6.1999, W. Grosser - MD; 1 male, Greece, Peloponnese, Killini Mts., Kefalari, 7.5.2000, S. Kalúz leg. - ML; 2 females, Greece, Peloponnese, Itilo, 10 km S Areopoli, Taigetos Mts., 800 m, 10.6.1999, W. Grosser - MD, ML; 2 males, Greece, Peloponnese, Gythio, 13.5.2000, 15.5.2000, S. Kalúz leg. - SM; 1 male, Greece, Peloponnese, Taygetus Mount, 14.5.2000, S. Kalúz leg. - SM; 1 male, Greece, Peloponnese, Taygetus Mount, Gorani, 12-13.5.2000, S. Kalúz leg. - SM; 2 males, Greece, Peloponnese, Menalon Mts. - N, Panagitsa, 19-20.5.2000, S. Kalúz leg. - SM, ML; 1 female, Greece, Peloponnese, Menalon Mts. - N, Panagitsa, 10.5.2000, I. Rychlik leg. - SM; 1 male, 1 female, Greece, Peloponnese, Foloï oak forest, 25.6.2022, V.Yu. Gazanchidis - ML; 2 females, Greece, Peloponnese, Foloï oak forest, 25.6.2022, V.Yu. Gazanchidis - VG.

Distribution. Greece, Peloponnese.

Etymology. The new taxon is dedicated to Milan Sláma - the preeminent specialist on European Cerambycidae.

6. *Agapanthia (Epopetes) boeberi michaeli* Sláma, 1986

(Figs. 7-10)

Agapanthia cynarae michaeli Sláma, 1986: 469 - "Crete, Voutas", "Crete, Theriso", "Crete, Gazi"; Sláma & Slámová, 1996: 138 - Kriti (Crete): "Voutas, Theriso"; Althoff & Danilevsky 1997: 40 - Crete; Danilevsky, 2012a: 153.

Agapanthia cynarae, Oertzen, 1886: 285, part - Attika, Parnasson, Kephallonia, Crete; Demelt, 1967: 64, part - Greece.

Agapanthia (Epopetes) cynarae michaeli, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 215, part. - Greece (Kriti); Shapovalov, 2012: 187 - "Crete"; Steiner & Schmid, 2013: 2, part. - "Griechenland"; Danilevsky, 2020b: 301, part. - Greece (Crete).

Type locality. Crete, Voutas.

Elytral pubescence is very poor, similar to the previous subspecies; elytra widely rounded apically; narrow basal parts of many antennal joints under fine white pubescence rather dark reddish; elytral and pronotal puncturation distinctly denser; body length in males: 11.8-17.0 mm, body width: 3.0-4.5 mm, body length in females: 13.8-17.0 mm, body width: 3.4-4.7 mm.

Material. 1 male (paratype), 1 female (paratype), Crete occ., Voutas, 6.1984, J.& M. Sláma - MD.

Distribution. Crete Island.

Figures 1-6: **1-2.** *Agapanthia (Epoptes) boeberi boeberi* (Fischer von Waldheim, 1806): 1 – male, Kazakhstan, Uralsk, Rozhkovo, 100 m, 15.6.1999, M. Danilevsky (Photo by M. Danilevsky, Moscow); 2 – female, Chelyabinsk Region, S. Troitsk, Zolotaya Sopka, 54°02'46"N, 61°36'34"E, 4-6.6.2013, E.Yu. Zakharova (Photo by M. Danilevsky, Moscow). **3-4.** *Agapanthia (Epoptes) boeberi diversicornis* Pic, 1927, **nom. rest.**: 3 - male, Albania, Vlorë county, 3.5 km E Vagalat, 39°45'43"N, 20°09'39"E, 80 m, 6.5.2021, O. Pak leg; 4 – female with the same label. **5-6.** *Agapanthia (Epoptes) boeberi slamai* Lazarev, **ssp. n.**: 5 – Holotype, male, Greece, Peloponnese, Kariopolis, near Gythion, 2.6.1981, M. Sláma; 6 – Paratype, female, Greece, Peloponnese, Kariopolis, near Gythion, 3.6.1981, M. Sláma.

Figures 7-10. *Agapanthia (Epoptes) boeberi michaeli* Sláma, 1986: 7 – Paratype, male, Crete occ., Voutas, 6.1984, J.&M. Sláma; 8 – Labels, paratype, male; 9 – Paratype, female with the same label; 10 – Labels, paratype, female.

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